

Stochastic Collision Probability Assessment of Vessels with Padma Bridge Piers under Random Initial Conditions

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ABSTRACT

Ship-bridge collisions remain a persistent global safety concern, often leading to severe structural damage, vessel losses, and risks to passenger safety. The Padma Multipurpose Bridge in Bangladesh, a 6.15 km long structure supported by 42 piers, has experienced several vessel impacts during and after construction, mainly involving ferries. While the structural damage has been minor, the repeated incidents underscore the urgent need for a quantitative risk assessment in this critical waterway. This study presents a probabilistic framework for evaluating the collision risks of small cargo vessels with Padma Bridge piers, focusing on the influence of vessel manoeuvrability under random initial conditions. Ship dynamics were modelled using Nomoto's K-T manoeuvring equations, with trajectories stochastically simulated via the Runge-Kutta fourth-order method. A total of sixty-two million simulations were performed across varying rudder angles (-15° to $+15^\circ$) and speeds (6–10 knots), with the navigation domain divided into 14 subregions around piers 9 to 18. The simulation typically takes approximately 50 hours to complete on a standard laptop computer. Results show that collision probability increases significantly with larger rudder angles and higher speeds, with piers 9, 10, 16, and 17 identified as high-risk zones. Conversely, central courses were found to minimise collision likelihood, offering safer navigation pathways. The findings are consistent with historical incidents, demonstrating the model's validity and underscoring the importance of manoeuvring discipline in confined waterways. Beyond the Padma Bridge case, the proposed stochastic framework provides a transferable methodology for assessing ship-structure collision risks in complex riverine or coastal environments, supporting both navigational safety management and bridge protection strategies.

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1. Introduction

Ship-bridge collisions represent a critical

safety concern in inland and coastal waterways worldwide. Such incidents can damage ships and bridge structures, threaten

passenger safety, disrupt transport networks, and impose high economic costs. Historical events, including the collapse of the Sunshine Skyway Bridge in Florida (1980) and the Francis Scott Key Bridge in Baltimore (2024), underscore the catastrophic potential of vessel-bridge impacts (Burkett and Mesmer, 2025). Even when collisions do not result in structural collapse, frequent minor impacts degrade infrastructure resilience and erode public confidence in transport safety. With the increasing scale of inland navigation and maritime traffic, especially in developing economies, reliable methods for quantifying and mitigating collision risks have become a pressing research priority.

The Padma Multipurpose Bridge, commonly known as the Padma Bridge, is a landmark infrastructure project in Bangladesh that spans 6.15 kilometres across the Padma River. Supported by 42 piers-40 located in the river and two transitional piers at the landward

ends-the bridge consists of 41 spans, each measuring 150.12 meters. Figure 1 shows the location of the bridge on Google Maps. It connects the country's south-western and north-eastern regions, playing a pivotal role in socio-economic development by enhancing trade, transport, and regional integration. However, since its construction and commissioning, the bridge has experienced multiple collision events involving ferries and small cargo vessels. Although the piers have sustained only superficial damage, these recurring incidents highlight vulnerabilities in vessel manoeuvring practices and waterway management. Given the river's strong currents, dense traffic, and limited navigational aids, the probability of collisions remains a serious concern. Therefore, a systematic risk assessment is essential for safeguarding the bridge structure, protecting passengers, and ensuring uninterrupted navigation along one of Bangladesh's most important waterways.

Figure 1: Padma Bridge and its surrounding areas (Google Maps, 2025)

During the construction phase, up until the inauguration, vessels had been colliding with the piers of the Padma Bridge at various locations. On July 23, 2021, ferry Shah Jalal collided with Pier No. 17 when it was

travelling from Banglabazar to Shimulia around 9:30 am. The master claimed the steering wheel became dislocated due to an electrical circuit breakdown and a strong river current. Twenty out of a hundred-plus

passengers were injured in the accident (Nafiu, 2021). On August 9, 2021, ferry Bir Shrestha Jahangir collided with pier no. 10 while travelling on the Banglabazar-Shimulia route. Five passengers were injured, two cars and one truck were damaged in the accident (FE Online Desk, 2021). Again, on August 13, 2021, ferry Kakoli collided with pier no. 10 around 6:45 am due to a strong current, causing the vessel to lose control. Although there were no casualties, the collision caused

concrete to shed from the pile cap (UNB News, 2021). In the same month, on August 31, 2021, the ferry Bir Shrestha Jahangir's flagstand broke after allegedly hitting the span between pillars 2 and 3 (The Business Standard, 2021). Figure 2 presents the ferry Bir Shrestha Jahangir colliding with a pier of the Padma Bridge. Figure 3 shows the damage to the ferry Shah Jalal from the collision with pier no. 17 of the Padma Bridge.

Figure 2: Moments before the collision between the ferry Bir Shrestha Jahangir and a pier of the Padma Bridge (JUST News BD, 2021)

Figure 3: Hole in the lower part of the ferry Shah Jalal due to collision (Nafiu, 2021)

Despite these collisions, the Padma Bridge authorities confirmed the collisions did not significantly damage the structure. The bridge was designed to withstand impacts from vessels up to 4,000 tonnes, while the ferries involved weighed approximately 1,000 tonnes (Akhter, 2022). Only surface damage to concrete plaster was reported in most cases. Therefore, in the context of this study, we are primarily concerned with casualties and the damage to vessels from the impact of a collision.

Globally, one of the most notable recent collisions was that of a container ship, the Dali, which collided with the Francis Scott Key Bridge on March 26, 2024, causing the bridge to collapse. The ship lost electric power when it was very close to the bridge; consequently, it lost manoeuvring control and collided with one of the bridge piers. As a result, the bridge suffered a catastrophic collapse. The vessel had poor maintenance, and her rudder was unavailable, among other causes, at the time of the emergency. This tragic accident resulted in the deaths of six maintenance workers who were on the bridge at the time (National Transportation Safety Board, 2024).

This work aimed to study cases of collisions where ships lose manoeuvring control very close to obstructions, and there is a high chance of collision if the vessel is left to continue on its current trajectory. Since the piers of the Padma Bridge are prone to collisions, assessing the relevant risk factors, especially the types and sizes of the ships travelling in the region, is essential. The main types of vessels that navigate through Padma are inland waterway vessels, primarily ferries, launches, and cargo vessels (Wheeler et al., 2010). Motorcycle ferries, passenger launches, tourist and charter speedboats, fishing skiffs,

and country boats ply in this region. Cargo lighters or construction barges frequently travel across the piers of the Padma Bridge around once every two days. All of the collision cases observed up until now were collisions of ferries with piers of the Padma Bridge. Since the primary design consideration for the Padma Bridge involves inland cargo vessels, this work has focused on studying the probable cases of collisions between cargo vessels and the piers of the Padma Bridge (Akhter, 2022).

The length of the larger cargo vessels varies from 60 to 85 meters, while the smaller ones range from 30 to 40 meters. However, this study focused on smaller cargo vessels, as smaller ships are generally more prone to damage upon collision than larger ships due to differences in structural strength, mass, inertia, energy absorption capacity, and damage distribution.

2. Literature Review

Research on ship-bridge collisions has evolved through several stages, beginning with structural impact studies. Early works modelled collision forces, energy absorption, and pier resilience to inform protective design measures, such as fenders and dolphins. Standards, including those from the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) and the Permanent International Association of Navigation Congresses (PIANC), emerged from this tradition. The AASHTO framework, for instance, incorporates factors including vessel frequency, deviation probability, geometric collision probability, and collapse probability to estimate annual bridge failure risk (Winters and Knott, 2025). Case-based structural analyses demonstrated that vessel

impacts at specific pier locations could induce stresses beyond material limits, leading to design recommendations such as extended pier lengths and vessel speed restrictions (Wilson et al., 2015).

A second line of research emphasised statistical and probabilistic assessments, often based on historical collision records. Models utilising Poisson processes, Bayesian belief networks, and probabilistic frequency analysis have been developed to quantify collision likelihood, incorporating traffic intensity, river geometry, and environmental conditions (Gucma, 2009; Hänninen & Kujala, 2012). For example, Hänninen & Kujala (2012) demonstrated the critical role of officer decision-making and human factors in determining collision risk. More recently, data-driven approaches have been integrated: Son et al. (2020) analysed AIS traffic distributions to establish safe passage distances with statistical confidence intervals, while Wang et al. (2020) employed decision trees and neural networks to predict high-risk vessel types and validate probabilistic estimates against observed outcomes. These methods provide valuable insights but remain constrained by data availability and limited treatment of real-time vessel dynamics.

Parallel to these approaches, significant progress has been made in ship manoeuvring and dynamic models. The foundation was laid by Nomoto et al. (1957), who introduced a transfer function-based method for evaluating ship steering quality and developed the well-known Nomoto first-order K-T model, later refined with experimental data across different ship types (Nomoto, 1960). The model describes yaw-sway motion using empirically derived indices, K and T, which

became central to predicting ship trajectories. Subsequent researchers extended the model: Son (1982) incorporated yaw-sway-roll coupling, Yoshimura (1986) addressed shallow-water effects, and Yoshimura (2011) later examined the impact of roll motion. Journée & Pinkster (2002) simplified the estimation of manoeuvring indices, making the model more practical for engineering applications. These developments advanced the application of manoeuvring theory to navigation safety, though most studies remained deterministic, using fixed rudder inputs or initial conditions.

The extension of manoeuvring models gave rise to more complex frameworks such as the MMG model, the Modular model, and the Abkowitz model, enabling higher degrees of freedom and improved hydrodynamic fidelity. Intelligent traffic simulators also emerged, such as the system developed by Hasegawa et al. (2012), which integrates ship dynamics into navigation safety management and accident prevention. Hybrid approaches combining probabilistic analysis with dynamic models have been explored in parallel. For instance, Wu et al. (2019) applied fuzzy logic systems to integrate ship, bridge, and environmental variables for real-time collision risk alerts. Yu and Guan (2021) improved probabilistic assessments by embedding ship simulator data, reflecting more realistic navigation behaviours and human responses.

Comprehensive reviews, such as Guçma (2009) and Wheeler et al. (2010), have emphasised the integration of structural, probabilistic, and dynamic perspectives into unified frameworks. More recent surveys (e.g., Zhang & Meng, 2018) have underscored

progress in probabilistic and simulation-based collision avoidance but have also identified ongoing challenges, including uncertainty quantification, validation of safety measures, and applicability in complex riverine settings. Collectively, the literature review illustrates a gradual progression from static structural assessments to probabilistic and dynamic models. However, stochastic vessel dynamics remain underutilised, particularly in rivers with strong currents and dense traffic. This study addresses that gap by employing Nomoto's manoeuvring model within a large-scale probabilistic simulation framework, offering a more realistic and transferable approach to ship-bridge collision risk evaluation in the context of the Padma Bridge.

3. Mathematical Formulation

3.1. The Nomoto Model

Initially, the equations for ship manoeuvring problems were developed based on the principles of motion, specifically

$$(m - X_{\dot{u}}) \dot{u} - X_{u\dot{u}}(u - U) = 0 \tag{3.1}$$

$$(m - Y_{\dot{v}}) \dot{v} - Y_{vv} + (mx_G - Y_{r'}) \dot{r} + (mU - Y_r) r = Y_{\delta} \delta \tag{3.2}$$

$$(mx_G - N_{\dot{v}}) \dot{v} - N_{vv} + (I_z - N_r) \dot{r} + (mx_G U - N_r) r = N_{\delta} \delta \tag{3.3}$$

We can rewrite equations (3.2) and (3.3) in the form:

$$(m - Y_{\dot{v}}) \dot{v} - Y_{vv} = Y_{\delta} \delta - (mx_G - Y_{r'}) \dot{r} - (mU - Y_r) r \tag{3.4}$$

$$(mx_G - N_{\dot{v}}) \dot{v} - N_{vv} = N_{\delta} \delta - (I_z - N_r) \dot{r} - (mx_G U - N_r) r \tag{3.5}$$

Solving equations (3.4) and (3.5) for \dot{v} and v yields,

$$v = \frac{(m - Y_{\dot{v}}) [N_{\delta} \delta - (mx_G U - N_r) r - (I_z - N_r) \dot{r}] - (mx_G - N_{\dot{v}}) [Y_{\delta} \delta - (mU - Y_r) - (mx_G - Y_{r'}) \dot{r}]}{Y_{\dot{v}}(mx_G - N_{\dot{v}}) - N_{\dot{v}}(m - Y_{\dot{v}})} \tag{3.6}$$

$$\dot{v} = \frac{Y_{\dot{v}} [N_{\delta} \delta - (mx_G U - N_r) r - (I_z - N_r) \dot{r}] - N_{\dot{v}} [Y_{\delta} \delta - (mU - Y_r) r - (mx_G - Y_{r'}) \dot{r}]}{Y_{\dot{v}}(mx_G - N_{\dot{v}}) - N_{\dot{v}}(m - Y_{\dot{v}})} \tag{3.7}$$

Differentiating equation (3.6) with respect to time and hence equating it to equation (3.7), results in the following equation:

$$T_1 T_2 \ddot{r} + (T_1 + T_2) \dot{r} + r = k \delta + k T_3 \delta \tag{3.8}$$

hydrodynamic forces and moments acting on a ship. This model is known as the 'Hydrodynamic Force Model'. Later, another approach was taken, which came to be known as 'Response Models'. They are regarded as an improvement over earlier models due to their more straightforward structure of equations and more accurate coefficients, which better represent real-world manoeuvring characteristics. These models are primarily used in problems associated with ship motion control and in designing control mechanisms, such as rudders. The model employed in this work, the 'Nomoto Model', falls under the category of Response Models, which the Japanese professor Kensaku Nomoto developed in 1957.

The format of the equations of the Nomoto Model is more straightforward than that of the Hydrodynamic Force Model. The coefficients used in the equations directly relate to the manoeuvring characteristics, and they can be used to evaluate a ship's manoeuvrability. The model makes use of the following equations:

Here,

$$T_1 T_2 = \frac{(m - Y_{\dot{v}}) - (I_z - N_r) - (m x_G - N_{\dot{v}}) v (m x_G - Y_{\dot{r}})}{-Y_v (m x_G U - N_r) + N_v (m U - Y_r)} \quad (3.9)$$

$$T_1 + T_2 = \frac{-Y_v (I_z - N_r) + N_v (m x_G - Y_{\dot{r}}) + (m - Y_{\dot{v}}) (m x_G U - N_r) - (m x_G - N_{\dot{v}}) (m U - Y_r)}{-Y_v (m x_G U - N_r) + N_v (m U - Y_r)} \quad (3.10)$$

$$K = \frac{-Y_v N_{\delta} + N_v Y_{\delta}}{-Y_v (m x_G U - N_r) + N_v (m U - Y_r)} \quad (3.11)$$

$$K T_3 = \frac{-Y_{\delta} (m x_G - N_{\dot{v}}) + N_{\delta} (m - Y_{\dot{v}})}{-Y_v (m x_G U - N_r) + N_v (m U - Y_r)} \quad (3.12)$$

$$T_3 = \frac{K T_3}{K} = \frac{-Y_{\delta} (m x_G - N_{\dot{v}}) + N_{\delta} (m - Y_{\dot{v}})}{-Y_v N_{\delta} + N_v Y_{\delta}} \quad (3.13) \text{Comparing the}$$

expressions of the coefficients A, B, C in the above equations and the coefficients $T_1, T_2, (T_1 + T_2)$ in equations, noting that φ_1 and φ_2 are given by equation (3.8), we can find the relationship

between φ_1, φ_2 , and T_1, T_2 as follows:

$$\frac{C}{A} = \sigma_1 \sigma_2 = \frac{1}{T_1 T_2} = \left(-\frac{1}{T_1}\right) \left(\frac{1}{T_2}\right) \quad (3.14)$$

$$-\frac{B}{A} = \sigma_1 + \sigma_2 = \frac{T_1 + T_2}{T_1 T_2} = \left(-\frac{1}{T_1}\right) + \left(-\frac{1}{T_2}\right) \quad (3.15)$$

Equation (3.8) denotes a response model of the second order. It expresses the relation between yaw motion and the rudder angle. Hence, it can describe the yaw motion response to the control action. Assuming that the ship is approximately fore and aft symmetrical, equation (3.8) can be further reduced to a response model of the first order. For a ship that is approximately fore and aft symmetrical, one obtains the following relations,

$$\begin{aligned} X_G &\approx 0 \\ Y_r &\approx 0 \\ N_v &\approx 0 \\ N_{\dot{v}} &\approx 0 \\ Y_{\dot{r}} &\approx 0 \end{aligned}$$

Hence, it follows that,

$$K = \frac{N_{\delta}}{N_r}$$

$$T_1 + T_2 \approx \frac{I_z - N_{\dot{r}}}{N_r} - \frac{m - Y_{\dot{v}}}{Y_v}$$

$$T_3 \approx \frac{m - Y_{\dot{v}}}{Y_v}$$

$$(T_1 + T_2 - T_3) \approx -\frac{I_z - N_{\dot{r}}}{N_r}$$

$$I_z - N_{\dot{r}} - N_r \times r = N_{\delta} \times \delta \quad (3.16)$$

$$-\frac{I_z - N_{\dot{r}}}{N_r} \times \dot{r} + r = -\frac{N_{\delta} \times \delta}{N_r} \quad (3.17)$$

Denoting $T = T_1 + T_2 - T_3$, the following relation is obtained,

$$T \dot{r} + r = K \delta \quad (3.18)$$

3.1.1 Estimation of the Manoeuvring Indices, K and T

The first-order indices, K and T , can be determined from the experimental results of two test trials: the Turning Test Data and the Zig-Zag Manoeuvring Data. Generally, no linear relationship will be found between φ'' or φ' and δr when analysing manoeuvring test data because of the ship's non-linear behaviour. K and T depend on the rudder angle, δ .

3.1.1.1 Turning Test Data

The Nomoto Model stands as:

$$T\ddot{\psi} + \dot{\psi} = K\delta_r \tag{3.19}$$

The value of the indices, K and T , can be determined from a turning test with a rudder action, as shown in Figure 4 below. This figure shows ψ' vs. time and the resulting ψ vs. time curve, from which the time-domain limit is understood.

Figure 4: Course and ship turn rate during a turning test

It is evident from the figure that two time domains must be considered. One is $0 \leq t \leq t_1$, and the other is $t \geq t_1$. Replacing the value of the rudder angle, $\delta_r = \frac{\delta_a}{t_1}t$, yields a solution:

$$\dot{\psi} = \frac{KT\delta_a}{t_1} \cdot \left(e^{-\frac{t}{T}} - 1 + \frac{t}{T} \right) \tag{3.20}$$

However, this solution only applies for $0 \leq t \leq t_1$. For the solution of $t \geq t_1$, replacing the rudder angle, $\delta = \delta_a$, the equation takes the form of,

$$T\ddot{\psi} + \dot{\psi} = K\delta_a \tag{3.21}$$

Now, the solution of the above equation turns out to be,

$$\dot{\psi} = C_e \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{T}} + K\delta_a \tag{3.22}$$

For $t = t_1$, both solutions should have been the same value:

$$\dot{\psi} = \frac{KT\delta_a}{t_1} \cdot \left(e^{-\frac{t}{T}} - 1 + \frac{t}{T} \right) = C_e \cdot e^{-\frac{t}{T}} + K\delta_a \tag{3.23}$$

From which follows the so far unknown constant C_e :

$$C_e = \frac{KT\delta_a}{t_1} \cdot \left(e^{-\frac{t}{T}} - 1 \right) \tag{3.24}$$

The value of constant C_e yields a solution for $\dot{\psi}(t)$ at interval $t \geq t_1$:

$$\dot{\psi} = \frac{KT\delta_a}{t_1} \cdot \left(e^{-\frac{t}{T}} - \frac{e^{\frac{t_1}{T}}}{t} + \frac{t_1}{T} \right) \quad (3.25)$$

3.1.1.2 Zig-Zag Test Data

Similar to the turning test data, zig-zag manoeuvring data can also be utilised to determine the values of Nomoto's first-order indices, K and T . Figure 5 below represents the rate of turn versus time of a typical Zig-Zag manoeuvring test, along with the time domain, which indicates the boundary for performing integration.

Figure 5: Integration boundaries for analysing zig-zag manoeuvres

Now, Nomoto's indices, K and T , can be written as follows:

$$T\ddot{\psi} + \dot{\psi} = K(\delta_c + \delta_r) \quad (3.26)$$

Where δ_c is a correction angle, introduced to compensate for the asymmetry of the ship when sailing in a straight line. Now, integrating between $t = 0$ and $t = t_e$ with $\dot{\psi} = \dot{\psi}_0$ at both boundaries results in:

$$T\dot{\psi} \Big|_{\dot{\psi}_0}^{\dot{\psi}_e} + \psi \Big|_{\psi_0}^{\psi_e} = K\delta_c t_e + K \int_0^{t_e} \delta_r dt \quad (3.27)$$

And,

$$\psi_e = K\delta_c t_e + K \int_0^{t_e} \delta_r dt \quad (3.28)$$

By differentiating equation (3.28), it can be found that:

$$\dot{\psi}_e = K\delta_c \dot{t}_e + K \int_0^{t_e} \delta_r dt \quad (3.29)$$

Further differentiation of equation (3.28) gives the following result:

$$\ddot{\psi}_e = K\delta_c \ddot{t}_e + K \int_0^{t_e} \delta_r dt \quad (3.30)$$

Finally, numerical integration of $\int_0^{t_e} \delta_r dt$, the values of K and δ_c are determined. Additionally, the value of T is determined by integrating the equation several times. However, experimental data obtained from the Zig-Zag test prove to be more valuable, and it is convenient to use for determining the values of the manoeuvring indices, K and T .

3.1.1.3 Empirical values of K and T

The manoeuvring indices, K and T , are made dimensionless by applying multiplication and divisional operations with the ship's length, L , and surge speed, U_0 . The dimensionless parameters are K' and T' with the following expressions:

$$K' = \frac{K \times L}{U_0}$$

$$T' = \frac{T \times U_0}{L}$$

Figure 6 below is a graphical representation of the distribution of the indices K' and T' , concerning the size of ships for various types, as published by Nomoto in the First Symposium on Ship Manoeuvrability in 1960. The spread of the data indicates that K' does not depend much on the size of the ship, but T' increases with the size of the ship.

Figure 6: Distribution of non-dimensional K and T indices (Journée et al., 2002)

At times, the overshoot angle is used to analyse the results of the data obtained from Zig-Zag manoeuvre tests. However, Nomoto has noted that the overshoot angle is almost directly proportional to K'/T' , with the rudder angle, δ_r , remaining constant.

Figure 7: Relationship between steering quality indices, K' and T'

Figure 7 supports Nomoto's assertion, showing that the parameters K' and T' are more helpful in analysing Zig-Zag Test data than the overshoot angle. This is because the relevant points lie between 0.75 times and 1.25 times the mean line.

3.2 Runge-Kutta 4th order Method

The Runge-Kutta 4th-order method (RK 4) is a widely used numerical technique for solving ordinary differential equations (ODEs), including systems of ODEs, which are often encountered in ship trajectory determinations, such as the first-order ordinary differential equation, $T \frac{dr}{dt} + r = K \delta_r \delta - r$, which represents the 'Nomoto Model'.

In the context of ship trajectory simulation, the state variables are the turning rate (r) and the heading angle (Ψ), both of which are updated using the Runge-Kutta 4th-order method (RK4). The system can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dr}{dt} &= f_1(r, \delta_r) \\ \frac{d\Psi}{dt} &= f_2(r) \end{aligned} \quad (3.31)$$

For the turning rate (r), the RK4 update is applied as:

$$\begin{aligned} k_{1r} &= h \cdot f_1(r_n, \delta_r) \\ k_{2r} &= h \cdot f_1\left(r_n + \frac{k_{1r}}{2}, \delta_r\right) \\ k_{3r} &= h \cdot f_1\left(r_n + \frac{k_{2r}}{2}, \delta_r\right) \\ k_{4r} &= h \cdot f_1\left(r_n + \frac{k_{3r}}{2}, \delta_r\right) \end{aligned} \quad (3.32)$$

The updated result is as follows:

$$r_{n+1} = r_n + \frac{1}{6}(k_{1r} + 2k_{2r} + 2k_{3r} + k_{4r}) \quad (3.33)$$

For heading angle (Ψ), the equations are the following:

$$\begin{aligned} k_{1\Psi} &= h \cdot f_2(r_n) \\ k_{2\Psi} &= h \cdot f_2\left(r_n + \frac{k_{1r}}{2}\right) \\ k_{3\Psi} &= h \cdot f_2\left(r_n + \frac{k_{2r}}{2}\right) \\ k_{4\Psi} &= h \cdot f_2(r_n + k_{3r}) \end{aligned} \quad (3.34)$$

$$\Psi_{n+1} = \Psi_n + \left(\frac{1}{6}\right)(k_{1\Psi} + 2k_{2\Psi} + 2k_{3\Psi} + k_{4\Psi}) \quad (3.35)$$

Here, the functions can be described as:

$$f_1(r, \delta_r) = \frac{K_{coefficient}}{T_{coefficient}} \cdot \delta_r - \frac{r}{T_{coefficient}} \quad (3.36)$$

And,

$$f_2(r) = r \quad (3.37)$$

4. Methodology

4.1 Overview of the Workflow

There had been frequent collisions with several piers of the Padma Bridge at different locations, resulting in significant damage to the vessels. Therefore, it was necessary to investigate the collision phenomenon across a region with high collision probability. In this regard, the authors identified a probable collision space on the river, containing ten bridge piers, specifically piers numbered 9-18 in a near horizontal alignment. The position of the initial X-coordinate of the Centre of Gravity

of the ship and the ship's speed were randomised to capture the nature of the probabilistic analysis. The randomness in the ship's initial position was uniform, as those were generated using the 'random.uniform' function. The probabilistic rather than the deterministic approach was employed in this study.

The authors conducted a field study to determine the size and speed of the cargo vessels moving across the piers. It was necessary to obtain the values of the non-dimensional K and T coefficients, for the 'Nomoto Model' relies on those manoeuvring indices to determine the ship's trajectory.

Afterwards, the 'Nomoto Model' equations were solved using the Runge-Kutta 4th order method with a Python script, and the trajectories of the ships were plotted in a 2-dimensional space. The Python program checked whether collisions took place by comparing the positions of the ships at intervals against the edges and vertices of the octagonal piers. This work was conducted for initial unchanged rudder angles ranging from -15° to $+15^\circ$ at 5° intervals for speeds of 6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 knots. The authors determined the vessel's speed to be approximately 8 knots and considered four additional speeds, taking into account the findings of the field study.

The choice of the initial unchanged rudder angles reflects the nature of the trajectories and the resulting percentages of collisions when those rudder angles were applied. The average percentages of collisions and radius of curvature of the turn of the vessel change marginally when the initial rudder angle changes by 1° or so. Only when the difference in rudder angles is 5° or more, there is a significant change in the resultant average percentages of collisions, which is worthy of study. That is why initial rudder angles were considered at an interval of 5° . Initial rudder angles from -15° to 15° were considered to compare the results when the rudder angles were applied on the port or starboard side. The upper limit of -15° or 15° takes into consideration the observations of the field study and standard real-world maritime practices. Therefore, the initial position of the X coordinate of the initial Centre of Gravity and a record of yes or no corresponding to collision or no collision were recorded for a specific initial unchanged rudder angle across different speeds in Excel worksheets. With this information, the authors conducted a

probabilistic analysis to determine the probability of a ship colliding for an initial, unchanged rudder angle at several speeds across regions with piers. Later, the authors compared that data and made several recommendations.

4.2 Observations from Field Study

During the construction phase, when collisions were frequent, the ferries collided with the bridge piers. To understand the situation, the authors investigated the route to study the condition of the marine traffic. The authors conducted a field investigation at noon in January 2024. The authors took a round trip across the piers along the Mawa-Kaorkandi route and recorded where vessels were observed to be stationary or in motion. The authors noticed a ferry, fishing vessels, tourist boats, and a cargo vessel during the trip. The authors determined from visual observation that the cargo vessel spotted was approximately 40 meters in length, 7 meters in width, and weighed around 600 tonnes. Additionally, the ship's speed was approximately 8 knots. Upon consultation with the relevant personnel, it was determined that the speed of those vessels ranged from 6 to 10 knots.

4.3 Solution of Nomoto Model

Initially, the authors rearranged the model's equation into the $\frac{dy}{dx} = f(x, y)$ format to make it workable for the Runge-Kutta 4th order method. Hence, it was arranged as follows:

$$T \frac{dr}{dt} + r = K\delta_r$$

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = \frac{K_{coefficient}}{T_{coefficient}} \cdot \delta_r - \frac{r}{T_{coefficient}}$$

By substituting the values of K and T indices, the form of the differential equation becomes:

$$\frac{dr}{dt} = A\delta_r - Br$$

where δ_r is the independent variable, and the solution gives subsequent values of r . Then, the heading angle was determined using the relation: $d\Psi = r dt$. After solving for $d\Psi$, a ship's trajectory is obtained by multiplying the X and Y components of velocity, V_x and V_y , at each time step.

$$V_x = V \times \cos(d\Psi)$$

$$V_y = V \times \sin(d\Psi)$$

$$S_x = V_x \times t$$

$$S_y = V_y \times t$$

The ship's trajectory was determined by plotting the values of S against time.

4.4 Simulation Space for Plotting the Trajectory of Ships

The area of interest, consisting of 10 piers (piers no. 9 to 18), was simulated in a 2-dimensional space using MATPLOTLIB, a graphical package built with Python. The area was divided into 14 locations, each with a width of 136.6 meters. Thus, the area of interest had a width of 1913 meters and a height of 672 meters. The width of each location is presented in Table 1 below for a clearer understanding of the simulation results.

Table 1: The distribution of locations along the river width

Location no.	Pier no.	Location no.	Pier no.
L1 (0-136.6 m)	9	L8 (956.9-1093.5 m)	Most of 14
L2 (136.7-273.3 m)	No pier	L9 (1093.6-1230.2 m)	Little of 14
L3 (273.4-410.0 m)	10	L10 (1230.3-1366.9 m)	15
L4 (410.1-546.7 m)	11	L11 (1367-1503.6 m)	16
L5 (546.8-683.4 m)	Partial of 12	L12 (1503.7-1640.3 m)	No pier
L6 (683.5-820.1 m)	Partial of 12	L13 (1640.4-1777 m)	17
L7 (820.2-956.8 m)	13	L14 (1777.1-1913 m)	18

Figure 8 below is a 2-dimensional representation of the space where the ship

trajectories were simulated. The vertical lines indicate the boundaries of the locations.

Figure 8: Simulation Space for Ship Trajectory

4.5 Detection of Collision

The vertices of the piers were determined as plotted in 2-dimensional space, and from these vertices, equations for the piers' edges were generated by forming straight-line equations from two given points. When the authors ran the code once, it completed the record of 100,000 iterations at a time for an initial, unchanged rudder angle corresponding to a speed. This way, a record of 1 million is taken for an initial, unchanged rudder angle in a direction corresponding to a speed. Once the code executes the given commands, a random X coordinate for the initial Centre of Gravity within the space is generated, which is randomised uniformly within the width of the space. However, the initial component of the Centre of Gravity along the Y-direction remained constant for all the iterations. The vessel's trajectory is determined by solving the equations of the Nomoto Model and plotted using Matplotlib.

The Python code computed the vertices of the

ship at each iteration via a rotation matrix. The code checks for collision with the vertices and edges of the piers more frequently as the ship approaches the piers, thereby utilising computational power more efficiently. The code checks for the ship's 2-dimensional surface position at each time step against the vertices and edges of the piers. Suppose there is an intersection of the ship surface with the edge of the piers. In that case, a collision is recorded in an Excel worksheet against the randomly generated X coordinate of the initial Centre of Gravity of the ship. If there is no intersection against the ship's initial Centre of Gravity, a record is generated with no collision against that initial position. If there is no collision, the simulation would stop after a specific period of crossing the piers.

Figure 9 below represents the simulated trajectory for a 10 knot and 5° initial rudder angle, where it is evident that there is no collision and the ship stops after some time crossing the piers.

Figure 9: Detection of no collision for an initial rudder angle at a speed. Similarly, when a collision is detected, the simulation stops, and a collision message is printed at the top right corner of the simulation space. Figure 10 below represents the detection phenomena at 10 knots and 5° rudder angle.

Figure 10: Detection of collision for an initial rudder angle at a speed

4.6 Probabilistic Analysis

Deterministic models utilise fixed variables to predict outcomes when randomness is minimal, yielding straightforward and predictable results. In contrast, probabilistic models are necessary when randomness has a significant impact on a system, as they incorporate uncertainty, account for complex variable interactions, and provide distributions of possible outcomes. Probabilistic models are especially valuable for simulating costly or context-specific problems, saving resources, and handling situations where deterministic approaches would be impractical.

After data were generated for 1 million cases corresponding to each rudder angle and speed, count if conditions were used in the Excel worksheet to separate the cases of a single location corresponding to a speed, and the number of collisions for those cases was also determined. Hence, the number of collisions was divided by the total number of

cases for a location to get the probability of collision for that location corresponding to a ship. Hence, the distribution of the percentage of collisions was calculated across those 14 regions for a single speed.

5. Results and Discussion

5.1 Results

Table 2 is given below to help get an overview of the collision scenario. The table records the average percentages of collisions at each of the five considered speeds (6,7,8,9, and 10 knots) against their corresponding rudder angles and initial C.O.G of the ship along the Y direction. The criteria for setting the values for initial C.O.G along the Y direction were so that the ships could pass across the piers safely and not make a loop before passing the piers. The values of the non-dimensional K and T indices were introduced to show the turning ability of the ships with respect to time at different speeds.

Table 2: Average Percentages of Collisions for Rudder Angle and initial C.O.G

Speed	Rudder angle	K	T	Initial C.O.G along the Y direction		Avg. % of collision	
				Upstream	Downstream	Upstream	Downstream
10 knot	0°	0.153	10.626	20	652	28.88	28.89
	+5°			20	652	37.04	40.35
	-5°			20	652	39.12	37.69
	+10°			130	532	47.87	50.66
	-10°			130	532	50.56	47.62
	+15°			190	471.5	55.35	58.85
	-15°			190	471.5	54.27	56.70
9 knot	0°	0.138	11.803	20	652	28.88	28.89
	+5°			20	652	37.52	40.00
	-5°			20	652	39.20	38.15
	+10°			130	532	46.84	49.57
	-10°			130	532	49.95	47.13
	+15°			190	471.5	51.21	53.06
	-15°			190	471.5	52.54	52.22
8 knot	0°	0.122	13.278	20	652	28.88	28.89
	+5°			20	652	35.59	32.58
	-5°			20	652	36.85	33.71
	+10°			130	532	46.01	49.54
	-10°			130	532	50.22	48.70
	+15°			190	471.5	47.47	48.02
	-15°			190	471.5	47.39	44.90
7 knot	0°	0.107	15.175	20	652	28.88	28.89
	+5°			20	652	36.42	39.27
	-5°			20	652	38.76	38.69
	+10°			130	532	46.76	49.66
	-10°			130	532	49.82	46.43
	+15°			190	471.5	45.97	44.96
	-15°			190	471.5	45.41	44.19
6 knot	0°	0.092	17.704	20	652	28.88	28.89
	+5°			20	652	36.62	39.30
	-5°			20	652	38.94	37.93
	+10°			130	532	46.96	48.95
	-10°			130	532	48.97	46.91
	+15°			190	471.5	45.02	46.23
	-15°			190	471.5	46.70	46.78

Tables 3 to 7 are introduced below to show the probability of collision at each of the 14 locations for the initial C.O.G belonging to those locations. Every table, from 3 to 7, is

dedicated to one of the five considered speeds (6, 7, 8, 9, and 10 knots) and has 16 columns. Out of those 16 columns, columns 3 to 16 indicate the location-wise distribution of the

collision probability corresponding to a rudder angle and a direction of travel (upstream or downstream). For example, the data in column 3, row 2 of Table 5.2 reads 0.40. It means that for a ship whose initial rudder angle was 0°, whose initial Centre of Gravity was within L1 (0 m to 136.6 m) and which moved in the upstream direction, its probability of colliding with a pier of the

Padma Bridge is 40 percent. The values are marked in red to indicate that they belong to locations with the highest or second-highest percentages of collisions. On the other hand, values are marked green to indicate that they belong to locations with the lowest or second-lowest percentages of collisions. The interpretation of the results is discussed in the next section.

Table 3: Percentage of collisions for speed 10 knots

Rudder Angle (°)	Direction (up/down stream)	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9	L10	L11	L12	L13	L14
0	Up	0.40	0	0.41	0.40	0.11	0.30	0.40	0.23	0.18	0.41	0.35	0.05	0.41	0.40
0	Down	0.41	0	0.40	0.41	0.10	0.30	0.40	0.22	0.17	0.40	0.35	0.06	0.40	0.41
5	Up	0	0.57	0.32	0.27	0.57	0.45	0.14	0.58	0.56	0.13	0.46	0.58	0.24	0.33
5	Down	0.23	0.59	0.48	0.18	0.56	0.60	0.17	0.44	0.60	0.28	0.31	0.60	0.40	0.18
-5	Up	0.31	0.57	0.38	0.20	0.58	0.51	0.13	0.51	0.57	0.19	0.38	0.57	0.31	0.26
-5	Down	0	0.58	0.25	0.34	0.59	0.38	0.23	0.58	0.50	0.15	0.53	0.59	0.18	0.41
10	Up	0	0.72	0.54	0.29	0.63	0.66	0.29	0.50	0.73	0.34	0.40	0.73	0.47	0.27
10	Down	0.53	0.75	0.34	0.43	0.74	0.46	0.30	0.71	0.59	0.31	0.59	0.70	0.31	0.48
-10	Up	0.53	0.73	0.32	0.44	0.72	0.43	0.29	0.72	0.55	0.28	0.61	0.68	0.28	0.48
-10	Down	0	0.73	0.53	0.31	0.66	0.65	0.30	0.53	0.74	0.33	0.41	0.74	0.44	0.30
15	Up	0.19	0.48	0.80	0.44	0.42	0.76	0.56	0.36	0.68	0.69	0.36	0.55	0.81	0.36
15	Down	0.88	0.50	0.44	0.80	0.62	0.43	0.68	0.75	0.46	0.56	0.86	0.43	0.44	0.69
-15	Up	0.76	0.48	0.32	0.71	0.61	0.31	0.58	0.68	0.36	0.47	0.75	0.41	0.35	0.67
-15	Down	0.18	0.51	0.88	0.50	0.45	0.81	0.60	0.42	0.71	0.73	0.44	0.58	0.85	0.43

Table 4: Percentage of collisions for speed 9 knots

Rudder Angle (°)	Direction (up/down stream)	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9	L10	L11	L12	L13	L14
0	Up	0.40	0	0.41	0.40	0.11	0.30	0.40	0.23	0.18	0.41	0.35	0.05	0.41	0.40
0	Down	0.41	0	0.40	0.41	0.10	0.30	0.40	0.22	0.17	0.40	0.35	0.06	0.40	0.41
5	Up	0	0.57	0.31	0.25	0.56	0.44	0.13	0.56	0.58	0.13	0.44	0.57	0.25	0.32
5	Down	0.24	0.60	0.47	0.17	0.57	0.58	0.15	0.45	0.59	0.28	0.32	0.59	0.39	0.20
-5	Up	0.31	0.58	0.37	0.21	0.57	0.50	0.14	0.52	0.57	0.18	0.40	0.57	0.30	0.27
-5	Down	0	0.61	0.25	0.34	0.60	0.38	0.22	0.60	0.50	0.15	0.53	0.59	0.18	0.41
10	Up	0	0.71	0.53	0.28	0.61	0.66	0.27	0.50	0.72	0.33	0.38	0.71	0.47	0.26
10	Down	0.52	0.72	0.32	0.43	0.73	0.44	0.29	0.73	0.56	0.29	0.60	0.70	0.29	0.48
-10	Up	0.54	0.72	0.30	0.43	0.71	0.43	0.30	0.71	0.55	0.28	0.61	0.67	0.27	0.49
-10	Down	0	0.73	0.53	0.29	0.64	0.65	0.29	0.52	0.73	0.35	0.39	0.73	0.47	0.29
15	Up	0.19	0.47	0.74	0.39	0.39	0.73	0.51	0.30	0.67	0.64	0.30	0.55	0.73	0.31
15	Down	0.78	0.49	0.35	0.73	0.62	0.35	0.60	0.70	0.40	0.48	0.78	0.42	0.36	0.67
-15	Up	0.74	0.48	0.31	0.70	0.61	0.30	0.57	0.67	0.35	0.46	0.74	0.41	0.34	0.67
-15	Down	0.19	0.49	0.79	0.41	0.41	0.75	0.54	0.36	0.68	0.67	0.36	0.58	0.77	0.34

Table 5: Percentage of collisions for speed 8 knots

Rudder Angle (°)	Direction (up / down stream)	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9	L10	L11	L12	L13	L14
0	Up	0.40	0	0.41	0.40	0.11	0.30	0.40	0.23	0.18	0.41	0.35	0.05	0.41	0.40
0	Down	0.41	0	0.40	0.41	0.10	0.30	0.40	0.22	0.17	0.40	0.35	0.06	0.40	0.41
5	Up	0	0.56	0.32	0.25	0.56	0.45	0.13	0.55	0.57	0.13	0.44	0.57	0.26	0.33
5	Down	0.45	0.10	0.35	0.44	0.22	0.23	0.45	0.33	0.10	0.44	0.45	0.03	0.41	0.41
-5	Up	0.33	0.57	0.36	0.21	0.57	0.48	0.13	0.51	0.57	0.17	0.40	0.57	0.30	0.28
-5	Down	0.35	0.10	0.45	0.45	0.03	0.42	0.45	0.15	0.30	0.45	0.28	0.17	0.45	0.40
10	Up	0	0.71	0.53	0.28	0.62	0.66	0.28	0.49	0.72	0.34	0.37	0.71	0.47	0.26
10	Down	0.53	0.73	0.32	0.41	0.73	0.45	0.28	0.72	0.56	0.29	0.61	0.69	0.29	0.48
-10	Up	0.55	0.73	0.30	0.43	0.71	0.41	0.30	0.72	0.55	0.27	0.62	0.67	0.26	0.49
-10	Down	0	0.72	0.52	0.29	0.64	0.65	0.30	0.52	0.71	0.32	0.40	0.73	0.46	0.28
15	Up	0.19	0.48	0.67	0.31	0.36	0.68	0.43	0.24	0.66	0.55	0.23	0.56	0.67	0.20
15	Down	0.68	0.48	0.24	0.62	0.61	0.24	0.48	0.68	0.30	0.37	0.68	0.42	0.25	0.68
-15	Up	0.66	0.48	0.22	0.63	0.60	0.22	0.50	0.67	0.29	0.38	0.67	0.40	0.26	0.66
-15	Downs	0.19	0.49	0.67	0.31	0.37	0.68	0.43	0.25	0.68	0.56	0.23	0.56	0.67	0.23

Table 6: Percentage of collisions for speed 7 knots

Rudder Angle (°)	Direction (up /down stream)	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9	L10	L11	L12	L13	L14
0	Up	0.40	0	0.41	0.40	0.11	0.30	0.40	0.23	0.18	0.41	0.35	0.05	0.41	0.40
0	Down	0.41	0	0.40	0.41	0.10	0.30	0.40	0.22	0.17	0.40	0.35	0.06	0.40	0.41
5	Up	0	0.56	0.32	0.24	0.57	0.43	0.13	0.57	0.57	0.13	0.44	0.57	0.25	0.32
5	Down	0.16	0.56	0.60	0.19	0.43	0.61	0.29	0.31	0.61	0.42	0.19	0.61	0.44	0.07
-5	Up	0.32	0.57	0.37	0.21	0.56	0.49	0.13	0.51	0.57	0.18	0.39	0.56	0.29	0.28
-5	Down	0	0.55	0.16	0.48	0.60	0.23	0.37	0.60	0.37	0.24	0.60	0.49	0.16	0.57
10	Up	0	0.72	0.53	0.27	0.61	0.67	0.28	0.48	0.71	0.34	0.37	0.71	0.47	0.26
10	Down	0.53	0.74	0.32	0.44	0.72	0.45	0.28	0.72	0.56	0.29	0.60	0.69	0.29	0.47
-10	Up	0.54	0.72	0.30	0.44	0.71	0.41	0.30	0.71	0.53	0.27	0.60	0.68	0.28	0.49
-10	Down	0	0.72	0.54	0.28	0.63	0.66	0.29	0.51	0.72	0.33	0.39	0.73	0.47	0.28
15	Up	0.18	0.48	0.67	0.30	0.35	0.67	0.43	0.23	0.66	0.55	0.23	0.56	0.66	0.21
15	Down	0.18	0.48	0.67	0.30	0.36	0.66	0.42	0.23	0.67	0.54	0.21	0.59	0.65	0.22
-15	Up	0.67	0.47	0.23	0.62	0.60	0.23	0.50	0.66	0.28	0.39	0.66	0.40	0.26	0.66
-15	Down	0.19	0.49	0.66	0.31	0.36	0.66	0.43	0.23	0.66	0.54	0.22	0.58	0.66	0.22

Table 7: Percentage of collisions for speed 6 knots

Rudder Angle (°)	Direction (up /down stream)	L1	L2	L3	L4	L5	L6	L7	L8	L9	L10	L11	L12	L13	L14
0	Up	0.40	0	0.41	0.40	0.11	0.30	0.40	0.23	0.18	0.41	0.35	0.05	0.41	0.40
0	Down	0.41	0	0.40	0.41	0.10	0.30	0.40	0.22	0.17	0.40	0.35	0.06	0.40	0.41
5	Up	0	0.57	0.33	0.25	0.57	0.45	0.14	0.56	0.57	0.12	0.44	0.57	0.25	0.33
5	Down	0.24	0.59	0.48	0.16	0.55	0.59	0.16	0.41	0.58	0.28	0.31	0.58	0.39	0.18
-5	Up	0.32	0.57	0.37	0.21	0.56	0.50	0.12	0.51	0.57	0.17	0.39	0.57	0.30	0.27
-5	Down	0	0.58	0.24	0.34	0.59	0.37	0.25	0.58	0.49	0.15	0.54	0.58	0.17	0.43
10	Up	0	0.71	0.54	0.27	0.62	0.67	0.29	0.49	0.71	0.34	0.36	0.71	0.47	0.26
10	Down	0.53	0.73	0.31	0.43	0.72	0.45	0.28	0.71	0.55	0.27	0.59	0.68	0.27	0.48
-10	Up	0.54	0.71	0.31	0.44	0.72	0.43	0.29	0.71	0.54	0.28	0.61	0.66	0.28	0.49
-10	Down	0	0.72	0.52	0.29	0.62	0.65	0.27	0.49	0.71	0.34	0.38	0.72	0.46	0.27
15	Up	0.18	0.48	0.66	0.30	0.36	0.66	0.44	0.23	0.67	0.56	0.26	0.54	0.66	0.20
15	Down	0.66	0.49	0.22	0.61	0.61	0.23	0.49	0.66	0.29	0.37	0.66	0.40	0.25	0.67
-15	Up	0.66	0.48	0.24	0.63	0.61	0.23	0.49	0.67	0.28	0.38	0.67	0.41	0.25	0.68
-15	Down	0.67	0.48	0.22	0.63	0.62	0.22	0.50	0.67	0.30	0.38	0.67	0.41	0.25	0.67

5.2 Interpretation of Results

1. For higher speeds, i.e., 9 and 10 knots, the average collision probability increases with an increase in the initial, unchanged rudder angle. However, for lower speeds, i.e., 6, 7, and 8 knots, the probability of collision increases at first with an increase in the initial unchanged rudder angle up to 10° . Still, it falls marginally when the rudder angle is 15° .
2. For the location-wise distribution of the collision probability, location no. 2 is the most hazardous location for a vessel to start its journey, with initial rudder angles up to 10° . Location 12 is the second most dangerous spot for a vessel to begin its journey, with initial rudder angles of up to 10° . However, no conclusive remark can be made for a 15° initial rudder angle.
3. From the viewpoint of the location-wise distribution of collisions, location 7 is the safest spot for a vessel to start its journey, particularly for initial rudder angles up to 10° . Generally, location 10 is the safest spot to begin the journey from for initial rudder angles of up to 10° .

5.3 Case Study

Between July and August 2021, four vessel collisions occurred with the piers of the Padma Bridge. The incidents are as follows: on July 23, ferry Shah Jalal struck pier no. 17 (Nafiu, 2021); on August 9, ferry Bir Shrestha Jahangir collided with pier no. 10 (Financial Express Online Desk, 2021); on August 13, ferry Kakoli hit pier no. 10 (United News of Bangladesh, 2021); and on August 31, Bir

Shrestha Jahangir again collided, this time in the space between piers 2 and 3 (The Business Standard Report, 2021). Pier no. 10 emerges as the most collision-prone from these events, followed by piers 17 and 3. Consequently, piers 9 to 18 were considered for trajectory simulations in this study. Simulation results indicate that starting locations 2 and 10 pose the highest risk for collisions across a range of initial rudder angles. Specifically:

1. At location 2, vessels moving upstream face pier no. 9 to the left and pier no. 10 to the right.
2. At location 12, pier no. 16 is to the left and pier no. 17 to the right.

The initial rudder angle influences the vessel's trajectory:

1. For upstream movement with a positive rudder angle, the vessel veers left, risking collision with the pier to the adjacent left.
2. Conversely, a negative rudder angle while moving upstream or a positive rudder angle while moving downstream shifts the vessel away from the correct starting location, increasing the risk of collision with the pier directly ahead.

At location 2, piers 9 and 10 are vulnerable when the initial rudder angle deviates from 0° up to 10° , aligning with real-world data that identifies pier no. 10 as highly collision-prone. Similarly, location 12 presents high risk, with piers 16 and 17 at adjacent positions, confirming pier no. 17's involvement in prior collisions.

Conversely, location 7 is identified as the safest starting point. Here, piers 12 and 13 are located adjacent to each other, at the left and

right positions, respectively, and no collisions have been reported at these piers— corroborating the simulation results.

The study validates that piers 10 and 9 are the most critical in terms of collision risk, followed by piers 17 and 16. Location 7 represents a low-risk starting point, consistent with observed collision data.

6. Conclusion

The analysis of vessel collisions with Padma Bridge piers demonstrates a clear pattern of risk associated with specific starting locations and rudder angles. Piers 10 and 9 emerge as the most collision-prone, followed by piers 17 and 16, consistent with reported accidents. Locations 2 and 12 represent high-risk starting points, while location 7 is the safest. Initial rudder angles significantly influence vessel trajectories, with deviations from 0° increasing the likelihood of collision at adjacent piers. The findings highlight that both pier placement and navigational parameters are critical in ensuring safe passage. The following recommendations are drawn:

1. Enhanced Navigation Guidance: Implement clear markers and signage for high-risk zones, especially near piers 9, 10, 16, and 17, to guide vessels safely through the bridge area.
2. Traffic Control Measures: Implement speed limits and establish controlled navigation channels near collision-prone piers to reduce the probability of accidents.
3. Vessel Manoeuvring Training: Provide targeted training for ferry operators on trajectory handling, especially regarding initial rudder angles and upstream/downstream navigation.

4. Collision Mitigation Structures: Consider installing fenders, dolphins, or other protective barriers at the most vulnerable piers to absorb impact and minimise damage.
5. Ongoing Monitoring: Continuously collect and analyse navigational and collision data to update risk maps and adapt safety measures as necessary.

To improve prediction and prevention of vessel collisions, it is recommended to develop a more sophisticated mathematical model that incorporates:

1. Non-linear Vessel Dynamics: Capture the effects of varying rudder angles, speed, and environmental forces (currents, wind, and waves) on vessel trajectories.
2. Probabilistic Collision Risk Assessment: Include uncertainties in vessel behaviour, human errors, and environmental variability to estimate collision probabilities more realistically.
3. Real-time Simulation Capability: Enables the dynamic analysis of vessel trajectories in various scenarios for decision support and training purposes.
4. Recommendations are further made for developing digital twins that incorporate wave data, wind data, and the actual ships.

Such an advanced model would provide a more accurate, predictive tool for maritime safety planning, bridge design improvements, and navigation guidelines, enabling proactive measures to prevent accidents rather than relying solely on reactive observations. These measures can collectively reduce the

likelihood of future collisions and enhance overall maritime safety in the vicinity of the Padma Bridge.

Author Contribution

Conceptualisation, Dr. Zobair Ibn Awal; methodology, Dr. Zobair Ibn Awal, Mahir Hasan; software, Mahir Hasan, Md. Emtiyaz Hossain; validation, Mahir Hasan, Dr. Zobair Ibn Awal, Md. Emtiyaz Hossain; formal analysis and investigation, Mahir Hasan, Md. Emtiyaz Hossain; data curation, Mahir Hasan, Md. Emtiyaz Hossain; writing—original draft preparation, Mahir Hasan; writing—review and editing, Dr. Zobair Ibn Awal, Mahir Hasan; supervision, Dr. Zobair Ibn Awal. All authors have read and agreed to the published version of the manuscript.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest among them.

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